

Hydrogen Adsorption on Chromium Borate and Oxide

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Chromium borate is not reduced by hydrogen in the temperature range of 200-600°, but it is decomposed to Cr₂O₃ and B₂O₃, decomposition becoming prominent from 500°.

With chromium borate, the uptake of hydrogen is maximum at 200°, but decreases with rise in temperature. Magnetic susceptibility results indicate that chemisorption is less at lower temperatures, but becomes prominent at 500° and 600°.

With Cr₂O₃, the uptake of hydrogen is relatively high, but the extent of chemisorption is less prominent at higher temperatures.

In investigating metal borate-hydrogen systems Khundkar and co-workers¹⁻⁴ have found the reaction between hydrogen and the borates of copper, nickel, cobalt, and silver follows the general reaction:

The reduction was found complete at 600° for nickel borate² and at 750° for the copper compound¹. Cobalt borate³, however, fused at higher temperatures and reduction was not complete even at 750°. In the case of silver borate⁴, reduction was rapid and was complete at 150°. The amount of hydrogen consumed was found in the above cases to be in excess of the amount required for reduction and the excess was accounted as undergoing "activated adsorption". The excess hydrogen taken up was relatively small in the case of copper, nickel, and cobalt borates and relatively high with silver borate.

With manganese borate⁵, MnB₄O₇, no reduction took place with hydrogen in the range of 200-600°, but a large quantity of the gas was adsorbed; the adsorption showed a positive temperature coefficient. From magnetic susceptibility data, a part of the hydrogen adsorbed was ascribed to chemisorption, but the major part of it was adsorbed in the lattice. Mn²⁺ has an electronic configuration of 1s² 2s² 2p⁶ 3s² 3p⁶ 3d⁵; during adsorption, one electron is added and the configuration changes to that of Mn⁺, which has an electronic configuration of 1s² 2s² 2p⁶ 3s² 3p⁶ 3d⁵ 4s¹.

If we take the case of Cr³⁺ having 1s² 2s² 2p⁶ 3s² 3p⁶ 3d³ and if hydrogen behaves in a similar way as that on manganese, there is a probability of higher adsorption on chromium borate. This, coupled with the fact that chromium sesquioxide has also a high free energy of formation and is consequently not reducible by hydrogen, prompted us to extend

1. Deb and Khundkar, *this Journal*, 1956, **33**, 555.
2. Huq *et al.*, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.* 1958, **21**, 81.
3. Jahan and Khundkar, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 7.
4. Khundkar *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1962, **39**, 333.
5. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1963, **40**, 0.

our study to this system also. Interesting observations have been made with the chromium borate and the sesquioxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Chromium Borate.—Chromium aminoborate was prepared by the method described by Khundkar and Haider⁶. Its analytical data conformed to the composition, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{B}_4\text{O}_7)_3 \cdot 3\text{NH}_3 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (Found: Cr, 12.0, B, 14.8; NH_3 , 5.3; H_2O , 29.6. Calc.: Cr, 11.7; B, 14.6; NH_3 , 5.7; H_2O , 30.3%). The aminoborate was heated in a porcelain crucible inside an electric pot furnace at $300^\circ \pm 10^\circ$ for 3-4 hr. On removing ammonia and water, a green crystalline product was obtained. For analysis, a weighed amount of the substance was dissolved in dilute HCl and aliquot portions were used in the determination of boron and chromium separately. Boron was determined volumetrically after adsorbing chromium on Zeo-Karb 225 and chromium, iodometrically. The compound corresponded to the composition, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$. (Found: Cr, 18.9, 18.5; B, 21.5, 21.3. Calc.: Cr, 18.3; B, 22.8%).

Preparation of Chromic Sesquioxide.—Chromium borate, prepared as above, was ignited to red heat in a platinum crucible for 1 hr. The product was allowed to cool *in vacuo* and washed thoroughly with dry methanol ($\times 3$) to remove free B_2O_3 . The oxide was analysed after fusion with sodium peroxide, followed by determination of the chromium iodometrically. (Found: Cr, 68.2, 68.5. Calc. for Cr_2O_3 : Cr, 68.4%).

Adsorption.—The apparatus used for studying the adsorption was more or less the same as that employed by Khundkar⁷, except that the system was connected at one end to a hydrogen Kipp with a hydrogen-purifying train and at the other end, to a gas-circulating pump instead of the $\text{CO}-\text{CO}_2$ determination train. An Edward high vacuum oil manometer, using Apiezon oil A, was also used together with the mercury manometer. The substance was placed in a platinum boat. To ensure complete reliability of the data, blank experiments were carried out in the temperature range of experiments. Before starting the experiments, the samples were degassed *in situ*.

To ascertain the reduction of the borate to metallic chromium and free boric oxide, the samples after hydrogen adsorption at different temperatures were analysed. The sample was washed several times with dry methanol to selectively extract any free boric oxide formed. The extract was estimated for boron. Chromium borate itself was not affected by dry methanol. (This was tested by refluxing a sample of the borate with anhydrous methanol and then determining the boron content in the extract). A procedure involving the selective separation of the metallic chromium formed, if any, from unchanged chromium borate could not be followed as both the borate and the metal were soluble in mineral acids.

To differentiate free B_2O_3 formed by reduction of the borate from that formed by decomposition, samples of the borate were heated *in vacuo* for 7 hr. in the range of temperature studied and the percentage of free B_2O_3 formed was found by extraction with dry methanol.

6. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1956, 284, 312.

7. *This Journal*, 1952, 29, 341.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made in a Curie-Chevenau type of magnetic balance, constructed in the laboratory. The measurements were made in pyrex glass tubes at the room temperature.

DISCUSSION

Adsorption of Hydrogen at Different Temperatures on Chromium Borate.—The uptake of hydrogen on samples (0.2 g.) of pure chromium borate was studied at 200°, 300°, 400°, 500°, and 600°. The plots of the volume of hydrogen adsorbed (corrected to N.T.P.) at different temperatures with progress of time are shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

At 200°, hydrogen uptake took place fairly uniformly right from the beginning, consuming a total volume of 32.5 ml in 7½ hr. There was no change in the colour of the product and no reduction took place. At 300°, uptake of hydrogen started after an initial induction period of about half an hour, continued more or less steadily, and ended with 30.2 ml after 7½ hr. At 400° after an induction period of over an hour, the uptake was only 24.0 ml during 7 hr. At 500°, 25.6 ml of hydrogen was taken up more or less uniformly in about 7½ hours, but the uptake during the last hour was very slow. At 600°, adsorption took place comparatively slowly and equilibrium was reached at 14.0 ml in about 6 hours. At 500° and 600°, the induction periods were shorter (ca. 15 min.).

At 200°, no induction period was noted probably due to high adsorption. The induction periods in the reactions at 300° and 400° may be ascribed to slow reaction rates. At 500° and 600°, the decomposition of the borate provided partly Cr₂O₃, the adsorption on which appeared to be without any induction.

Table I records the results of hydrogen uptake at different temperatures and the amount of free boric oxide, formed either as a result of reduction of the borate (as had

been observed in the case of copper, nickel or silver) or due to the decomposition of the borate itself. A set of experiments was also carried out, in which an equal amount of chromium borate was heated *in vacuo* at each temperature and the products were treated with methanol. Table I reveals that the free boric oxide obtained in the products of reaction of chromium borate with hydrogen at various temperatures is due to decomposition. From available thermodynamic data, Cr_2O_3 should require a very high temperature for reduction and from an analogy it may be argued that chromium borate also may not be reduced in the temperature range under study. Thus the hydrogen uptake may be ascribed to adsorption only.

TABLE I

Uptake of hydrogen by chromium borate at diff. temp.

$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ taken = 0.2 g. Duration of expt. = $7\frac{1}{2}$ hr.

Temp.	H_2 uptake.	% Free B_2O_3 in the product after H_2 uptake. Heating in vacuum.	
200°	32.5 ml	0.6	0.7
300°	30.2	1.9	2.0
*400°	24.0	2.3	3.
500°	25.6	26.7	25.5
*600°	14.0	49.0	50.0

*Uptake was virtually complete in 7 hr. (400°) and 6 hr. (600°).

TABLE II

Hydrogen uptake on Cr_2O_3 and chromium borate.

Temp.	H_2 adsorbed on		$X_g \times 10^6$ for product of adsorption on		
	Cr_2O_3 .	Cr-borate.	Cr_2O_3 .	Cr-borate.	Cr-borate heated in vacuum.
		Stock sample	26.17	14.11	..
200°	..	32.5ml	..	15.26	15.16
300°	42.9 ml	30.2	29.22	15.42	15.46
400°	58.2	24.0	32.84	15.34	15.00
500°	58.5	25.6	34.26	21.51	18.50
600°	55.6	14.0	34.11	27.54	23.00

Hydrogen Adsorption on Cr_2O_3 at Different Temperatures.—Uptakes on 0.05 g. samples of chromium sesquioxide ($\cong$ 0.2 g. of chromium borate) were studied in the temperature range of 300°-600°. The experiments were carried out for a period of 7 hr. Adsorption, however, continued beyond that time (vide Fig. 2). At 300°, the uptake is fairly uniform and reaches a value of 42.9 ml. At 400°, the uptake is faster and reaches a value of

58.2 ml. Adsorption is similar at 500° and 600°, reaching values of 58.5 and 55.6 ml respectively.

FIG. 2

Comparing total hydrogen uptake in about 7 hr. on chromium borate and chromium sesquioxide (Table II), adsorption on the latter was found much greater than in the former. Fig. 3 represents total uptakes on chromium borate and chromium sesquioxide at different

FIG. 3

temperatures (in 7 hr.) together with the percentage decomposition of chromium borate *in vacuo* in the same temperature range. These curves show that adsorption on Cr₂O₃

possesses a positive temperature coefficient from 300° to 400° and then tends to decrease between 500° and 600°. Hydrogen adsorption on chromium borate, however, shows a negative temperature coefficient in the range of temperature studied.

No definite conclusions may be made on this point. Incidentally, the work of Taylor and co-workers⁸ on the adsorption isobars exhibiting maxima and minima may be mentioned. Again for manganese oxide, there is a positive temperature coefficient, whereas with mixed manganous and chromium sesquioxide, the nature of adsorption is complex and different. The case of hydrogen adsorption on ZnO also shows two maxima between 200° and 700°.

On comparing the adsorption on chromium borate with decomposition at different temperatures, the uptake at 200° and 300° was found to be of the same order and mainly on the borate because of very little decomposition at these temperatures. Apparently, adsorption on chromium borate has a negative temperature coefficient. At 500°, there is a slightly larger uptake although, if the previous negative trend had been followed, the adsorption should have been less. This can be explained by the fact that at 500° there is a fairly large decomposition of the borate and as chromium sesquioxide, after its formation, takes up larger amounts of hydrogen, the observed uptake is slightly higher. At 600°, only 14.0 ml was adsorbed although here the concentration of Cr_2O_3 , formed by decomposition, was highest. This may be due to the fusion of the borate itself at this temperature. It should be pointed out that for chromium sesquioxide also, adsorption is somewhat smaller at 600° than at 500°.

Change in Magnetic Susceptibility of Chromium Borate and Oxide with Hydrogen Uptake.—The change in g. susceptibilities with hydrogen uptake on Cr_2O_3 and chromium borate together with the values for the stock samples are recorded in Table II. χ_g for chromium borate after hydrogen uptake at 200° increases by about one unit. After uptake at 300° and 400°, there is, however, no further increase and the values are more or less the same as that at 200°. Uptake of hydrogen at 500° causes a sudden increase in susceptibility by about six units from the value at 400°. At 600° also, there is a further increase of six units from the value at 500°. The increase in susceptibility values with adsorption at different temperatures may be ascribed to the slow decomposition of the borate, which, as previously mentioned, actually takes place. The decomposition of the borate would lead to the formation of chromium sesquioxide, which has a much higher susceptibility (Table II). This would therefore lead to an increase in the susceptibility of the product after hydrogen uptake at different temperatures. As a fairly large amount of decomposition is observed at 500° and 600° (25.5 and 50%), a jump of 6 units from 400° to 500° and a further 6 units from 500° to 600° is not unreasonable. To account for this increase, portions from the stock sample of the chromium borate were heated to different temperatures *in vacuo* and the susceptibilities of the cooled products were measured. Table II shows that the values between 200° and 400° are in fair agreement with those of the borate with adsorbed hydrogen. The values at 500° and 600° are, however, less by about 3 units and 4 units, respectively, from the corresponding values of the borate with adsorbed hydrogen. This means that at these two temperatures, the susceptibility increases are not due to the decomposition alone.

In the case of chromium sesquioxide (Table II, col. 4), on the other hand, susceptibility increases are pronounced up to 400°, after which it slows down. Of the total uptake

8. Cf. Trapnell, "Chemisorption", Butterworths, London, 1955, pp. 50-53.

of hydrogen (in the neighbourhood of 50 ml for 0.05 g.) by Cr_2O_3 , chemisorption should account for a small fraction. The fact that the increase of magnetic susceptibility for the borate is relatively small up to 400° indicates that the chemisorption on the borate is probably less than that on the oxide. Beyond 400° , the chromium borate decomposes to the sesquioxide, which itself has a higher χ_g values; the sesquioxide formed (by decomposition) likely tends to chemisorb some hydrogen. This may explain higher susceptibility values for experiments with chromium borate at 500° and 600° .

Mechanism of Adsorption.—Assuming that the orbital contributions are negligible, calculation of μ_B values for Cr_2O_3 and chromium borate indicates that the calculated values differ widely from the observed ones⁹. Therefore it is not possible to deduce (as was possible for manganese borate³) the number of unpaired electrons in the initial borate and its change with uptake of hydrogen. Incidentally, the increase in susceptibility is due to the incipient formation of the Cr^{2+} ions in the lattice of the borate and the oxide as a result of chemisorption. The hydrogen is believed to react with the oxygen ion to form hydroxyl ions and release one electron, which enters the unfilled 'd' level of the Cr^{3+} to form Cr^{2+} ions. The Cr^{2+} ion has been shown to have four unpaired electrons¹⁰, which would therefore increase the magnetic susceptibility. The mechanism of the process may be suggested as:

Hydrogen uptake on chromium borate is comparatively small with respect to manganese borate. Unlike manganese borate, its adsorption having a positive temperature coefficient, chromium borate shows a decrease in adsorption with increase of temperature, particularly in the range of 400° - 600° . Magnetic susceptibility further suggests that although at lower temperature the uptake is probably more as adsorption into the lattice (physical adsorption), from 400° to 600° chemisorption seems to play a more important role, probably through the formation of chromium sesquioxide by decomposition.

Uptake of hydrogen on the sesquioxide (40 to 60 ml for 0.05 g. Cr_2O_3) between 300° and 600° should be considered quite high. The major portion of the uptake should be absorption (or dissolution into the lattice), although some amount of the gas appears to have been chemisorbed. The chemisorption appears to be more significant up to 400° in the case of the oxide.

It should be noted that for a definite amount of the borate (or the corresponding amount of the oxide) there is a limiting volume of the gas that can be chemisorbed according to the mechanism postulated above. It is possible that in the case of sesquioxide, this limiting value is reached earlier, whereas for the borate direct chemisorption may be relatively slow, facilitated by the decomposition to the sesquioxide. This is a probable explanation of why chemisorption (as indicated by the magnetic susceptibility changes) continued at higher temperatures for the borate.

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9. Bhatnagar *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1433.
10. Moeller, "Inorganic Chemistry", John Wiley & Sons, 1954, p. 169.